

TEACHER'S ROLE IN TEACHING A LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7303017>

Annotatsiya: The ultimate purpose of assessment for learning is to create self-regulated learners who can leave school able and confident to continue learning throughout their lives. Teachers need to know at the outset of a unit of study where their students are in terms of their learning and then continually check on how they are progressing through strengthening the feedback they get from their learners. Students are guided on what they are expected to learn and what quality work looks like. The teacher will work with the student to understand and identify any gaps or misconceptions (initial/diagnostic assessment).

Kalit so'z: feedback, identify, misconceptions, initial/diagnostic assessment, responsibilities, correction, formative assessment

Although students or learners are becoming the center of lessons in modern teaching these days, teachers are the most important people in teaching a language. Because, you know, it is difficult to learn a language without a teacher's instructions for choosing a book, learning new vocabulary etc., feedbacks for the activities which has been done by learners. For example, if a learner chooses a book which is effortless or inappropriate for their level. In addition, a teacher can correct the learner's mistake. So teacher has got a lot of responsibilities for the lessons and learners like planning the lesson, correcting the mistakes, giving motivation for the learners, giving feedback for the mistakes.

However, there are some duties which are not appropriate for every subject teacher, like giving poster presentation during the lesson. What's more, the responsibilities can be different according to the age of learners. Furthermore, the number of students can change the methods which teacher can use. Planning a lesson is the most fundamental duty of the teacher. Because, there are a lot of learners but the time is limited, only 45 minutes. So, the teacher should plan the lesson in detail and appropriately. The teacher should pay attention to time management and make an effort to deploy every minute, every second. I think the best way of using the time effectively is scheduling. For example, 5 minutes for greeting and doing roll-call, 15 minutes for checking homework, 20 minutes for giving a new lesson, 5 minutes for giving homework. Second commitment of the teacher is making every learner participate in the lesson. Most teachers complain about participation because of the time. To put it another way, they

have not got enough time to ask every learner. However, any excuse cannot help to solve the problem. By contrast, trying to conquer the difficulty is the key for resolving it. That is why, instead of complaining, the teacher should be creative and find his or her own method which can help to gain his or her goal. For example, the “write and exchange” method: teacher will give time to all learners in order to do activities which are related to the lesson on their notebooks. The amount of the time is up to the activities (but it is better to be around 5 minutes). Then learners will exchange their work each other and check (they can also write feedback for the fellow pupil’s work). Maybe it takes 5 minutes. So, in about 10 minutes teacher can make every pupil take part in the lesson. However this method is suitable for the lessons of writing and reading and help to improve writing skill. The teacher can use the “debate” method in order to develop listening and speaking skills. In this method the teacher divide the pupils into groups that every group consists of 4 members. Next, he or she gives a topic for the first group (for instant, fast food). The group has 2 minutes for preparation. After 2 minutes the teacher give another topic (for example, environment) for preparation while the first group debate the topic each other for 2 minutes. After 2 minutes the teacher gives another topic (for example, study abroad) for the third group while the second group debate the topic for 2 minutes. If there are 16 pupils in the class the method takes only 10 minutes, in addition, every pupil can participate in the lesson. What’s more, the 2 group (8 pupils) can check the work of the group that debate.

A lesson plan is a teacher's detailed description of the course of instruction or "learning trajectory" for a lesson. A daily lesson plan is developed by a teacher to guide class learning. Details will vary depending on the preference of the teacher, subject being covered, and the needs of the students. There may be requirements mandated by the school system regarding the plan. A lesson plan is the teacher's guide for running a particular lesson, and it includes the goal (what the students are supposed to learn), how the goal will be reached (the method, procedure) and a way of measuring how well the goal was reached (test, worksheet, homework etc.).

On the hole, the teacher will correct during oral work through speech or during written work through writing. And in most cases, it can help learner prevent from repeating the mistake in the future. However, there are some situations where the teacher might prefer not to correct a learner’s mistake: in fluency work, for example, when the learner is in mid-speech, and to correct would disturb and discourage more than help. The recommendation not to correct a learner’s mistake during fluent speech is in principle a valid one, but perhaps an

over-simplification. There can be places where to refrain from providing an acceptable form where the speaker is obviously uneasy or 'floundering' can actually be demoralizing and gentle supportive intervention can help. Conversely, even where the emphasis is on getting the language right, the teacher may not always correct: in a grammar exercise, for example, if the learner has contributed an interesting or personal piece of information that does not happen to use the target form; also, when they have got most of an item right we may prefer not to draw attention to a relatively trivial mistake. Let's look at some techniques of oral correction following. Oral corrections are usually provided directly by the teacher; but they may also be elicited from the learner who made the mistake in the first place, or by another member of the class. Corrections may or may not include a clarification of why the mistake was made or may or may not require re-production of the acceptable form by the learner. The objective of the inquiry project suggested below is to ascertain which of these techniques are in fact most used in a selection of lessons taught locally, and which are preferred by learners. Some practical conclusions may be drawn from the results.

The best lessons, books, and materials in the world won't get students excited about learning and willing to work hard if they're not motivated. Motivation, both intrinsic and extrinsic, is a key factor in the success of students at all stages of their education, and teachers can play a pivotal role in providing and encouraging that motivation in their students. Of course, that's much easier said than done, as all students are motivated differently and it takes time and a lot of effort to learn to get a classroom full of kids enthusiastic about learning, working hard, and pushing themselves to excel. Even the best intentioned and educated teachers sometimes lack the skills to keep kids on track, so whether you're a new teacher or an experienced one, try using these methods to motivate your students and to encourage them to live up to their true potential. The abstract term 'motivation' on its own is rather difficult to define. It is easier and more useful to think in terms of 'motivated' learner: one who is willing or eager to invest effort in learning activities and to progress. Learner motivation makes teaching and learning immeasurably easier and more pleasant, as well as more productive: hence the importance of the topic for teachers. Various studies have found that motivation is very strongly related to achievement in language learning¹. The question then needs to be asked: which is the cause and which the result? In other words, does success in language breed its own motivation² or

¹ Marion Williams and Tony Wright. A course in language teaching: practice and theories. 1966

² Ruth Wajnryb. Classroom observation tasks; a resource book for language teachers and trainers. 2012

does previous motivation lead to success? Or both? The significant message of research in this area for teachers is sheer importance of the factor of learner motivation in successful language learning. The authors of classic study of successful language learning came to the conclusion that the most successful learners are not necessarily those to whom a language comes very easily, they are those who display certain typical characteristics most of them clearly associated with motivation. Some of these are:

1. Positive task orientation. The learner is willing to tackle tasks and challenges, and has confidence in his or her success.
2. Ego-involvement. The learner finds it important to succeed in learning in order to maintain and promote his or her own (positive) self-image.
3. Need for achievement. The learner has a need to achieve, to overcome difficulties and succeed in what he or she sets out to do.
4. High aspirations. The learner is ambitious, goes for demanding challenges, high proficiency top grades.
5. Goal orientation. The learner is very aware of the goals of learning, or of specific learning activities and direct his or her efforts towards achieving them.
6. Perseverance. The learner consistently invests a high level of effort in learning and is not discouraged by setbacks or apparent lack of progress.
7. Tolerance of ambiguity. The learner is not disturbed or frustrated by situations involving a temporary lack of understanding or confusion; he or she can live with these patiently in the confidence that understanding will come later.

In classrooms where assessment for learning, commonly called formative assessment, is practiced, students are encouraged to be more active in their learning and associated assessment. The ultimate purpose of assessment for learning is to create self-regulated learners who can leave school able and confident to continue learning throughout their lives. Teachers need to know at the outset of a unit of study where their students are in terms of their learning and then continually check on how they are progressing through strengthening the feedback they get from their learners. Students are guided on what they are expected to learn and what quality work looks like. The teacher will work with the student to understand and identify any gaps or misconceptions (initial/diagnostic assessment). As the unit progresses, the teacher and student work together to assess the student's knowledge, what she or he needs to learn to improve and extend this knowledge, and how the student can best get to that point (formative assessment). Assessment for learning occurs at all stages of the learning process. Most of the feedbacks we give our learners is ongoing correction and assessment, directed at specific bits of learner-produced

language with the aim of bringing about improvement; the type of evaluation involved here is sometimes called formative since its main purpose is to form: to enhance, not conclude, a process. Distinct from this is evaluation usually termed 'summative', where the teacher evaluates an overall aspect of learners' knowledge in order to summarize the situation: how proficient he or she is at a certain point in time, for example, and how much he or she has progressed during a particular course.

Summative evaluation may contribute little or nothing to the ongoing teaching/learning process, but it is a part of the teacher's job, something we need to know how to do effectively. Below are descriptions various ways of gathering information which will serve as a basis for assessment, and of some common criteria used for assessing it. The most common way of gathering information for assessment is through tests. The usual criterion is an arbitrary level which the learner is expected to have reached; and the result is generally expressed through percentages. Teacher is one of the most important people in society because they play an important role to bring up "the owners of the future", as a great American physician, philosopher dr. Michael J. Wallace claimed, "A great teacher plants the seeds of greatness in the minds of future generations³." Students often mimic a teacher's actions. So teachers should pay more attention to their jobs and responsibilities. Teachers teach in many ways including lectures, small group activities and hands-on learning activities. Teachers also play an important role in the classroom when it comes to the environment. Teachers are responsible for the social behavior in their classrooms.

To summarize the work that all school teachers have both academic and non-academic responsibilities to their pupils, sadly and unfortunately, most people only consider the academic responsibilities. They want their children's teachers to be the most knowledgeable of the subject matter they are teaching and also be the best in getting their kids to learn. Non-academic responsibilities, however, are just as important as academic responsibilities. Chances are that 20-30 years from now the non-academic moral lessons learned in the classroom will be remembered more than any academic knowledge.

³ Michael J. Wallace. Training foreign language teachers: a reflective approach. 1998

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